

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

METHODOLOGY FOR POSITIONING A GROUP OF GREEN ARTIFICIAL REEF
BASED ON A DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM, APPLIED IN THE
ESTUARY OF ARES-BETANZOS (NW IBERIAN PENINSULA)

Luis Carral¹, Carlos Alvarez-Feal², M^a Jesús Rodríguez-Guerreiro³, Andreina Vargas⁴,
Néstor Arean⁵, Rodrigo. Carballo⁶

¹²³*Universidade da Coruña. Grupo de Ingeniería Mixto*

⁴⁵⁶*Univ. de Santiago de Compostela, Área de Ingeniería Hidráulica, EPSE Campus
Univ. s/n, 27002 Lugo, Spain*

ABSTRACT

The Galician coast, and particularly its estuaries are ecosystems with a large biological production which require protection against the strong human pressure they suffer. Sustainability in fishing, shell fishing and recreational activities makes it advisable to develop measures such as the implementation of green artificial reefs (AR), which promote wealth and biodiversity in areas that stand out due to their productive capacity.

This document proposes a database management system (DBMS) to determine the position of the AR groups, based on geographic information systems (GIS) combined with high resolution numerical modelling and the development of computational algorithms. This system will be capable of analysing a large amount of spatial information regarding socio-economic and environmental factors that affect their installation.

The methodology considered in the DBMS takes into account *production factors* and *economic factors related to construction and maintenance*. This combination allows for the identification of the best locations for the functional development of the AR group with low implementation costs. The DBMS is applied to the Ria of Ares-Betanzos leading to the definition of the most suitable places for installing AR groups in this area.

Key words: Green Artificial Reef; Database Management System; Coastal Dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

Management of coastal areas has become an important concern for society due to the impact of human activities on the quality of the environment and of the water, and the need to optimise the aquaculture strategy (Bacher et al, 2003). These issues are of particular importance in Galicia (NW Spain) where the coastal areas, and especially its estuaries, have been recognized for their enormous uniqueness and importance as a support for population, productive activities, biological diversity and source of resources (Carral et al, 2018a).

1 Currently, the estuaries face the challenge of solving deep environmental and socio-
2 economic problems. The estuaries are high-capacity ecosystems that function as areas
3 for breeding and rearing marine organisms, many of them with a high economic value;
4 thus, it is of great interest to know the biological resources available in these
5 ecosystems, their internal dynamics and how to take advantage of them, protect them
6 and foster them effectively.
7

8
9 At the same time, one of the recommended measures to redress the loss of structural
10 complexity of the communities, the decrease of breeding areas and the alteration of
11 trophic networks is the implantation of artificial reefs (AR) in the environment (Seaman
12 *et al.*, 1989; Pickering, *et al.*, 1998; Barnabé, *et al.*, 2000; Haround and Herrera, 2000
13 and Whitmarsh, *et al.*, 2008); however, for their proper functioning it is utterly
14 necessary to take into account the possible impacts that these structures could have on
15 the aquatic environment (Sanders and Ruiz, 2007; Thiony *et al.*, 2011).
16
17

18
19 The placement of AR seeks to imitate some of the characteristics of a natural reef
20 (OSPAR, 1996) in order to obtain benefits such as: the **conservation of resources** by
21 reducing the pressure on existing reefs, the **restoration of the substrate** due to the
22 settlement of communities of invertebrates and algae in the AR, the **improvement in**
23 **fishing production** and even new applications such as **nautical tourism** and the
24 **recreational use of the sea** (Seaman, 2002; ;Seaman, 2007; Pears and Williams, 2005).
25
26
27
28

29
30 The goal of the PROARR Research Project is to design production and protection
31 modules for the construction of artificial reef groups adapted to the characteristics of the
32 Galician Region. As a result, green AR production and protection modules have been
33 developed, with the purpose of acting as agents for repopulating marine ecosystems and
34 recovering artisan fishery (Carral *et al.*, 2018a). The modules resulting from the project
35 have been patented (Fig. 2) (Carral *et al.*, 2018b), and the estuary of Ares-Betanzos has
36 been designated as the coastal area for the installation of an experimental reef group
37 (Carral *et al.*, 2018a).
38
39
40

41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58 Fig. 1. Location of the Ares - Betanzos estuaries in the NE region of Spain. Source: Own
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 The estuary of Ares-Betanzos is located between the estuaries of A Coruña and Ferrol
2 covering an area of roughly 72 km². It is the largest of the six estuaries located between
3 Cape Finisterre and Cape Prior, on the Northwest coast of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1).
4 It is a double estuary system (Asensio-Amor&Grajal-Blanco, 1981), with a volume of
5 0,75 km³ and a length of 19 km, consisting of two branches: i) Ares, with the estuary of
6 the river Eume and ii) Betanzos with the estuary of the river Mandeo.
7

8
9 The drainage of the Eume River located in the north part of the estuary (roadstead of
10 Ares and Redes), with an average discharge of 16.5 m³/s, is an important determinant of
11 the hydrographic conditions in the area (Prego et al, 1999): (Sánchez Mata et al, 1999).
12 In addition, the rivers Mandeo, Mendo and Lambre discharge through the Betanzos
13 marsh using the tidal channels, with an average annual flow of 14.1 m³s⁻¹. The two
14 sectors converge in an area of confluence that is freely connected to the Atlantic Ocean
15 through a 40m deep and 4km wide NW oriented mouth (Fig. 4).
16
17
18
19

20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31 Fig. 2- Artificial Reef Module PROARR. Source: Own
32
33
34

35 Previous studies in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos have focused on the diversity and
36 productivity of phytoplankton (Blanco, 1985; Mariño et al., 1985; Bode y Varela,
37 1998), nutrient distributions (Prego et al, 1999) and the physical-chemical structure of
38 the benthic environment (Sanchez-Mata et al., 1999) or the relationship between tidal
39 circulation and ecosystem metabolism (Villegas-Ríos et al., 2011). The latter authors
40 implemented a 2-D model to integrate the physical, chemical and biological data and
41 estimate the flows between the internal and external parts of the Ria. They concluded
42 that, *in comparison with the Rias Baixas, tidal circulation in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos*
43 *is positive even in upwelling and downwelling conditions as a result of the greater*
44 *importance of river flows* (Villegas-Ríos et al., 2011). In Lamas et al, (2019) the
45 hydrodynamic improvement of the PROARR modules is studied. In Rodríguez-
46 *Guerreiro et al (2019)* the temporal pattern of the biological development of an AR
47 located in this Ria was studied.
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55

56 2. METHODOLOGY AND OBJECTIVES 57

58 The goal of the present investigation is to identify the most appropriate areas for the
59 installation of an AR group in the Ria of Ares and Betanzos. To this end, a **database**
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 **management system (DBMS)** is developed, based on a **geographic information**
2 **system (GIS), combined** with a high-resolution numerical modelling and the
3 development of computational algorithms capable of analysing a large amount of spatial
4 information related to socio-economic and environmental factors affecting the
5 installation of an AR.
6

7 The methodology developed to determine the position of AR groups is based on the
8 consideration of *production factors* grouped by types of conditions: *excluding factors*,
9 *functional factors* (bathymetric, geomorphological, technical) and *the economic factors*
10 *of construction and maintenance* (table 1). This combination allows the identification of
11 the best places for the functional development of the AR with low implementations
12 costs.
13
14
15

16 **Excluding production factors** will be those that are related to the restrictive use within
17 each area, i.e., taken into consideration (protected natural areas, areas in use by
18 maritime transport / anchorage, areas for aquaculture / mussel farming). The individual
19 consideration of each of the indicated functions precludes the implementation of the AR
20 group in the areas in which one of these activities takes place, as shown in the exclusion
21 flow diagram (Fig. 3).
22
23
24
25

26 **Functional production factors** will be those that allow the full development of the
27 functions assigned to the AR, as defined by Carral et al (2018a). *The degree of*
28 *compliance with the established target benefits will act as a measure of this adequacy.*
29 In any case, the consideration of the functional factors will allow to classify each zone
30 according to its possibilities to reach the established objective benefits.
31
32
33
34

35 From the consideration of these latter functional factors, there is a classification into
36 **bathymetric** (depth), **geomorphological** (nature of the bottom) and **technical**
37 (magnitude of the currents that supplies the nutrients to the AR) factors, since all of
38 these are factors that condition the productivity of the AR.
39
40
41

42 An adequate magnitude of the water velocity and an appropriate hydrodynamic pattern
43 lead to an increase in the contribution and renewal of favourable nutrients for the larval
44 settlement (Perkol-Finckel et al., 2007) (Piedracoba et al, 2014), along with a reduction
45 in the sedimentation. Sedimentation is inversely related to the movement of water, and
46 it has been observed that a high rate of sedimentation is detrimental to the life of the
47 reef, inhibiting, among other factors, the exchange of nutrients and dissolved gases
48 (Smith et al., 1971; Aller y Dodge, 1974; Loya, 1976; Bak, 1978).
49
50
51
52

53 Finally, we must take into account **economic factors** that will affect the installation due
54 to the costs of implementation and conservation of the AR group.
55
56

57 Table 1 - Factors to be considered for the development of the green AR positioning
58 methodology. Source: Own
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

<i>Types of factors for green AA</i>	PRODUCTION			
	FACTORS PRODUCTION		ECONOMIC	
	EXCLUDING	FUNCTIONAL	CAPEX	OPEX
<i>Type of factors</i>	Maritime Traffic Anchoring areas Conservation Area Aquaculture Planning	Bathymetric, Geomorphological, Technical	Conception & Definition Design & Development Manufacturing Installation	Scientific Supervision Exploitation Costs
<i>Model</i>	EXCLUDING CHART FLOW DIAGRAM	NUMERICAL MODEL		

Fig. 3 - Flow chart for the application of exclusion criteria. Source: Own

In order to carry out an appropriate analysis of the established factors and thus determine the most suitable area for the positioning of an AR group in the Ria of Ares-Betanzos, it is necessary to generate and analyse a large amount of information, which is obtained through two procedures: i) collection of existing information; ii) implementation of high-resolution numerical models that are simulated during characteristic scenarios following specific methodologies. The resulting information is incorporated into a GIS (Geographic Information System), and several computational algorithms are developed allowing the manipulation of the data generated and computation of various parameters of interest. In this way, a powerful tool (DBMS) is made available leading to an informed decision-making process when defining the optimum location to install an AR group.

1 The specific methodologies used for the analysis of the different factors are presented in
2 sections 3 and 4. Section 5 presents the process carried out for the implementation of
3 the developed DBMS, as well as the results obtained, which are synthesized in the most
4 relevant conclusions in section 6.
5
6
7

8 3. SOCIOECONOMIC AND HYDROMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS 9

10 3.1. Use of the coastline

11 The specific characteristics of a coastal area may condition or even restrict the
12 installation of an AR. In this context, the Galician rias are characterized by their great
13 economic, social and environmental importance, which is associated with the presence
14 of numerous uses with which the operation of an AR must not interfere.
15
16
17
18
19

20 Among the existing uses, mussel farming is of particular relevance representing one of
21 the most notorious characteristics of the Galician coast, since the Galician Rias develop
22 40% of the European mussel culture and 15% of the world production of blue mussels
23 (Labarta et al., 2004). The Ria de Ares-Betanzos supports the production of 147 mussel
24 rafts concentrated mainly along the southern margin (Duarte et al, 2014) (Fig. 2), which
25 produce 10,000 tonnes of blue mussel *Mytilus Galloprovincialis* per year (Labarta et
26 al., 2004).
27
28
29
30

31 These mussel rafts affect the hydrodynamics of the rias, since they are built out of
32 eucalyptus beams attached to floats which are anchored to the sea bottom with concrete
33 blocks. Each raft has a maximum surface of 20 m x 25 m (500 m²) and contains up to
34 500 ropes with a length of between 6 and 12 m (Labarta et al., 2004). The distance
35 between neighbouring rafts within an AR group crop is about 100 m. In the case of
36 coastal ecosystems, several studies have investigated the influence of water circulation
37 on their production capacity (Grant et al, 1998; Grant y Bacher, 2001). According to
38 Shi et al. (2011), the aquaculture facility in the Sungo Bay (China) can cause a
39 reduction of 40% in the average surface current, decreasing the exchange of water with
40 the adjacent areas.
41
42
43
44
45
46

47 Therefore, understanding the hydrodynamics of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos and the
48 influence of aquaculture facilities on the circulation of water and *vice versa* has
49 important applications for the determination of the location of the AR groups.
50
51

52 However, the Galician rias are characterized by the presence of many other activities
53 along the coast, as well as numerous areas of great environmental value. In this study,
54 the following uses are considered excluding factors (Section 2): **i) areas of special
55 environmental protection (LIC and ZEPA areas); ii) bivalve (mussel) reserves; iii)
56 mussel raft polygons; iv) shellfish banks; v) fishing grounds; vi) aquaculture areas;**
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

vii) fish shelters; vii) maritime ferry routes and sea motorways; ix) maritime traffic; x) shipwrecks.

All the currently available information regarding the aforementioned uses is incorporated into the DBMS for its analysis. In this sense, an area is considered valid for AR installation when it does not interfere from the point of view of spatial occupation with the existing uses considered as excluding ones, and therefore represent an incompatibility with the presence of ARs. Thus, it must be pointed out that the present study does not consider excluding uses those that can be easily compatible with an AR, so that their normal operation also allows for the operation of AR groups, as it is the case for the large anchoring areas of the ports of Ferrol and A Coruña that exist in the Ria.

3.2. Morphological characteristics

In addition to the socio-economic and environmental aspects, there are a number of factors that may limit the functionality of ARs, such as the morphological characteristics. Within them, the aspects that are considered as fundamental characteristics that condition the operation and maintenance of an AR are: i) the depth and ii) the nature of the bottom, both being in close relationship.

Fig. 4 -Areas of the Rias de Ares-Betanzos with indication of dimensions and depths. The latter range between 2 and 43 m. Four geographic sectors have been outlined in the study area. The Ares sector, in the main part of the estuary, is 5 km long and 2 km wide with depths of 2 to 6 m. To the south of this area, in the *Betanzos sector*, which is sheltered from the south-west winds by the Bergantiños plateau and from the north and north-west winds by the Faladoira mountain range, is 7 km long and 5 km wide with depths ranging from 2 to 12 m. The area of *confluence* of the rivers, has a depth ranging between 10 - 20 m, with a smooth bottom as a result of the sedimentary contribution of the rivers. The mouth of the Ria, which is open to the continental shelf, is flanked on the margins by a reduced base rock and has a bottom made up of sedimentary sand with a depth of 43 m. Source: (Sánchez Mata et al, 1999)

The substrate of the sedimentary bottom of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos is distributed by three main factors: the system of water circulation within the estuary, the bathymetry and the balance of oceanic and continental flow to which the estuary is subjected to (Sánchez Mata et al, 1999).

1 The sedimentary structure of the Rias shows a high content of white and black sands
2 with signs of zinc silt. The distribution of clay content is determined by the bathymetry
3 of the two internal estuaries, characterized mainly by silt and clay at depths below 10 m
4 and a high content of organic matter and negative redox potentials in the central area
5 with abundant sand. The middle ría with depths between 20-30 m, and the outer ría
6 with more than 30 m, are mainly composed by gravel and sand (Fig. 9) (Sánchez Mata
7 et al, 1999)

8
9 For the consideration of the morphological factors, on the one hand, the information
10 currently available regarding the bathymetric characteristics of the area is incorporated
11 into the DBMS, for which the nautical charts of this area provided by the Instituto
12 Hidrográfico de la Marina (IHM) are used, as well as topographic data provided by the
13 Sociedade para o Desenvolvimento Comarcal de Galicia (SITGA, Xunta de Galicia). In
14 this context, the operating limits are established at approximately 10 - 25 m depth in
15 LAT (Lowest Astronomical Tide) conditions, without however a fixed criterion of
16 limits that totally restrict the installation of an AR. On the other hand, in relation to the
17 nature of the bottom, the distribution of the sediment types is analysed considering the
18 information provided by the IHM together with studies of high-spatial resolution
19 (Troncoso & Urgorri 1993). This information is also included in the DBMS for further
20 analysis. In this sense, although as in the case of the conditions related to the
21 bathymetric configuration, there are no fixed limitations for the installation of an AR, to
22 ensure its stability the most suitable areas are those with a mainly sandy bottom, and
23 rocky bottoms should be avoided as much as possible.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30

31 3.3. Hydrodynamic characteristics

32
33 The circulation of water bodies in the Galician Rias has been investigated by numerous
34 authors (Prego & Fraga 1992). The structure of the body of water within the estuaries
35 has a highly variable profile in response to variations in the river discharge, wind, tide
36 (Sánchez Mata et al, 1999), and even waves in its more exposed outer area, close to the
37 mouth. In this context, the importance of the different forcing factors can vary greatly
38 amongst estuaries, as well as between the different areas within it (Carballo et al.,
39 2009a; Iglesias et al., 2012), and even within the same area depending on the season
40 (Iglesias & Carballo, 2009; Iglesias & Carballo, 2011).
41
42
43
44
45
46

47 The hydrography of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos is normal (Prego & Fraga, 1992) with a
48 partially stratified mix of waters in two levels: a higher level and a lower level with
49 higher salinity (Bowden, 1980), and a gradual transition from inland waters to marine
50 waters (Pethick, 1984; Carter, 1988). According to McLusky (1989) the study area is a
51 euhaline estuary with annual salinities of bottom waters ranging between 31 and 37
52 PSU (Mora et al, 1994, 1996.).
53
54
55
56

57 The **general system of water circulation** of this ria is characterized by an important
58 input of groundwater that penetrates through the bottom from the open ocean (North
59 Atlantic central water). The initial movement is towards the east, where the mass of
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 water diverges in two currents. One of them is parallel to the coast towards the south of
2 the estuary, in the direction of the ria / marsh of the Mandeo River, where marine and
3 continental water mix. Then, it goes to the north and finally flows out dragging along
4 sedimentary particles from the Eume estuary in Pontedeume (Duarte et al., 2014). The
5 second current remains in the mouth of the ria, generating a cyclonic vortex due to the
6 bathymetric disturbances in the area, dragging the sediments towards a nearby
7 sedimentary area and depositing the coarse heterogeneous materials in the area of
8 exterior oceanic influence (Sánchez Mata et al, 1999).
9

10
11
12 The phenomenon of upwelling is seen seasonally through the effects of the upwelling
13 and downwelling events. The first in seasons of prevailing northern wind which, by
14 means of the Ekman pumping, produces an **upwelling** in the bottom of the estuaries and
15 an exit of the superficial waters as compensation (**positive residual circulation**)
16 (Duarte et al., 2014). During the **downwelling** season, in which the southern winds
17 prevail, there is an inversion of this circulation pattern, with Ekman pumping forcing
18 surface water to enter the platform which is compensated with an outflow through the
19 bottom layer (Piedracoba et al., 2005; Carballo et al., 2009b). Nevertheless, upwelling
20 and downwelling are also common outside their characteristic seasons (Iglesias et al.,
21 2008). The Ria de Ares-Betanzos, (Fig. 1), which is 4 to 7 times smaller than the Rias
22 Baixas and oriented in a different way, shows a low influence of the upwelling effect on
23 its bottom and, on the contrary, tidal circulation has a greater impact. Consequently, this
24 ria has a larger circulation flow than that of the Rias Baixas (Alvarez-Salgado et al.,
25 2011).
26
27

28
29
30
31
32
33 **Sanchez – Mata et al. (1999)** considers that tidal currents are more important within the
34 estuary than wind currents or those induced by waves, determining near surface
35 velocities of up to 0.89 ms^{-1} with a tidal range of 4.14 m. In further studies, peak
36 velocities are estimated to be of a significantly less intensity; in particular **Piedracoba et**
37 **al (2014)** estimate the maximum values at approx. $0.10 - 0.12 \text{ ms}^{-1}$.
38
39
40

41
42 The prevailing winds in the area under study are from north to east in spring and
43 summer and from south to south-west in winter and autumn (Fig. 1). Field observations
44 establish that northern storms have components that can disturb bottom sediments in the
45 entire area, with the exception of the innermost parts of the estuary (Sánchez Mata et al,
46 1999).
47
48

49
50 Based on the previous research presented, in this paper several high-resolution models
51 are implemented so that an exhaustive analysis of the hydrodynamics can be carried out
52 in the different study areas of interest, so that those with greater potential for installation
53 of an AR can be selected. As it has been shown, the hydrodynamics of the Galician rias
54 are the result of the complex interaction of diverse forcings (tide, contribution of
55 oceanic and continental waters, wind and, in certain situations, waves), which are
56 considered by the implemented models as current generating forcing agents.
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 To this end, various finite difference codes are implemented. First, the numerical model
2 DELFT3D FLOW (Deltares, 2010) that solves the Navier Stokes equations under the
3 Shallow Waters and Boussinesq assumptions, coupled to the transport equation. This
4 model allows the calculation of the circulation induced by all the aforementioned
5 forcings. However, in the case of waves, it needs information on the spatial distribution
6 of the radiation tensor resulting from the existing wave field under specific conditions.
7 To do this, the SWAN spectral model (Booij et al., 1999) is also implemented for the
8 wave propagation from deep water to the Ria.
9
10

11
12 The implementation of the DELFT3D model is done in its 2DH form, considering a 50
13 x 50 m computational mesh within the Ria (and therefore within the possible areas of
14 interest), progressively increasing its size towards the oceanic limits located
15 approximately 15 km from the mouth of the estuary at a depth of around 80 m (Figure
16 5). In relation to the SWAN model, two meshes are used: a coarse mesh for propagating
17 the wave field from deep water towards the mouth of the Ria, and a high-resolution
18 mesh within the Ria with the same characteristics as the computational mesh used in the
19 DELFT3D model (Figure 6). Finally, the bathymetric and topographic characteristics
20 incorporated within the DBMS are used to interpolate the depth values to the numerical
21 meshes.
22
23
24
25
26

27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46 Fig. 5 - FLOW3D numerical model grid. Only 1 in 3 grid lines are shown for clarity.. Source: own
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 6 -SWAN numerical model grids. Only 1 in 3 grid lines are shown for clarity.

The developed models are used to analyse the hydrodynamics of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos in three case studies: i) induced circulation in a situation of average conditions in the absence of wind and waves (Case A); ii) wind-induced circulation (Case B); iii) wave-induced circulation (Case C). The specific forcings that are considered in each case are as follows.

In Case A, the existing hydrodynamic conditions are determined considering the action of the tide during a complete cycle of average spring-neap tides, as well as the existence of annual average fresh water discharges and oceanic water mass with average thermohaline characteristics. The tide is introduced in the model considering the main tidal harmonics determined at the oceanic limit of the numerical mesh (Table 2); the characteristics of the ocean mass are obtained from the Villano-Sisargas buoy; finally, freshwater discharges are established according to previous studies (Prego et al., 1999; Sanchez-Mata et al., 1999) (Table 3).

Table 2. Main tidal constituents in the outer boundary limit of the hydrodynamic grid

Harmonic Constant	Amplitude (m)	Phase (°)
A0	2.2078	-
2SM	0.0116	289.39
Q1	0.0207	267.23
P1	0.0225	63.18
O1	0.0614	71.97
K2	0.1157	114.31
N2	0.2507	66.79
M2	1.1805	86.39
S2	0.4134	116.97

Table 3. Freshwater discharges and thermohaline conditions in Case A

Parameter	Outer boundary	Mandeo river	Eume river
Temperature (°)	16.0	13.3	11.7°
Salinity (ppt)	35.5	1	1
Q_m (m ³ s ⁻¹)	-	14.1 m ³ s ⁻¹	16.5 m ³ s ⁻¹

For the hydrodynamic analysis two specific situations are considered: the situation with the greatest magnitude of the current velocity during i) spring tides, V_s , and ii) neap tides, V_n . In Case B, the wind-induced circulation is studied, considering the action of N winds favourable to the existence of upwelling processes (Duarte et al., 2014) and strong winds of 10 ms⁻¹ according to previous studies in the Galician Rias (Iglesias & Carballo, 2010).

Finally, in case C, wave-induced currents are studied taking into consideration the conditions to which the Ria de Ares-Betanzos is more exposed (waves with a NW direction) and which in turn provide greater energy [spectral significant wave height, $H_{m0} = 3.27$ m; energy period $T_e = 9.11$ s] (Carballo et al., 2014).

As in the case of the previous conditions, the resulting information is incorporated into the DBMS for analysis. In this sense, although there are no established limits of the current velocity for the correct operation of an AR, it is estimated that its appropriate functioning requires the existence of velocities of 0.05 – 0.08 ms⁻¹ in the case of an AR with holes that are suitable for low speeds, and greater than 0.08 ms⁻¹ in the case of an AR with holes suitable for high velocities.

4. ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC FACTORS

4.1 Procedure

The economic benefits obtained from a natural environment are commonly presented in terms of several components that, taken together, constitute the total economic value (Turner and Adger, 1996); (Ledoux and Turner, 2002). This concept also applies to the development of AR functions in the case under study (Whitmarsh et al., 2008), with the additional requirement that the production must be environmentally sustainable (Table 4). So that for each possible location X_j some benefits will correspond, which, for the case of a green AR, Carral et al, (2018a) classifies as **direct, indirect, liabilities** $DB_{ij}, IB_{ij}, PB_{ij}$ (Table 4), including among them those related to the use of inert materials derived from the recycling of waste from maritime industries (Ferreño et al, 2013). As an indirect effect, the reduction in the environmental impact of related industries in the maritime sector should be considered, while it extends the passive effects by incorporating sustainability in the activity of the canning industry.

Table 4 - Shows the type of benefits derived from the generic implementation of green AR and the benefits derived from the proposed reef type (PROARR). In each case, establishing a basic distinction

between direct use, indirect use and passive use values. Source: Own elaboration based on (Carral et al, 2018a).

Location	Benefits	Direct -DBij	Indirect - IBij	Passive - PBij
	Definition	Immediately derived from the production and consolidation of the AA, so that the product can be obtained or enjoyed directly	Those that provide support for other economic activities or are a consequence of the effect on other components of the marine environment	Derived from the conservation of marine heritage and its availability for use by future generations
	Green AR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Extractive uses (artisan fishing and aquaculture) -Receive uses (surfing, diving, sport fishing) - Recycling of inert materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Fishing production through the protection of the marine habitat (plant substrate) -Diversification of overexploited fisheries - Protection of seaboard and coastline -Improvement in water quality by renewing nutrients -Reduction in the environmental impact of related maritime industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in biodiversity - conservation of the marine habitat, being preserved for use by generation - Sustainability of the industrial activities of maritime industries
Xj	PROARR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Extractive uses (artisan fishing and aquaculture) -Receive uses (surfing, diving, sport fishing) -Recycling of inert materials, waste from the maritime industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Fishing production through the protection of the marine habitat (plant substrate) -Diversification of overexploited fisheries -Improvement in water quality by renewing nutrients -Reduction in the environmental impact of the canning industry and the production of concrete aggregates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in biodiversity - Conservation of the marine habitat, being preserved for use by generation -Sustainability in the activity of the canning industry

From the consideration of the generic benefits indicated, the general expression (1) is proposed, which includes the total benefits derived from the implementation of a green AR as a consideration of the direct, indirect and passive benefits (Table 4)

$$Total\ Benefit\ F_j = Direct\ Benefit + Indirect\ Benefit + Passive\ Benefit \quad (1)$$

The very great difficulty to evaluate the passive and indirect benefits is clear, so when considering the immediate benefits derived from the production and consolidation of the AR, formula (2) is used (Carral et al, 2018a) which allows an estimation of the beneficial factors based on considering the direct factors that should be taken into account when implementing a green AR in a location "Xj" and considering the type of purpose and activity (Bi Ci) (2).

$$Direct\ Benefit\ DB_j = \sum_i^j A_{ij} B_{ij} C_{ij} \quad (2)$$

In this expression the coefficients A_{ij} – **type of AA** – (Conventional or Green), B_{ij} – type of purpose (extractive, recreational, derived from the use of inert materials and substitution of component materials) and the specific benefit C_{ij} - **benefit derived from each type of activity** (artisan fishing, aquaculture, surfing, diving, sport fishing, reuse of materials and recycling of materials), will be indicated by the contents of **table 5**

Table 5 contains the coefficients of formula (2) relative to the direct benefits derived from the implementation of AR group depending on the type of reef used and the purpose pursued. Source: Own

i	Conventional AR			Green AR		
	A_i	B_i	C_i	A_i	B_i	C_i
1	1	Extractive-1	Artisan Fishing	1	Extractive-1	Artisan Fishing
2			Aquaculture			Aquaculture
3		Recreative-1	Surfing		Recreative-1	Surfing
4			Diving			Diving
5			Sport Fishing			Sport Fishing
6	0	Substitution of materials-1	Reuse	Substitution of materials-1	Reuse	
7			Recycling		Recycling	

There are methodologies to address some of these benefit valuation problems (Pickering et al., 1998); (Milton and Holland, 2000), but additional techniques may be needed to broaden the scope of the evaluation so that the multiple objectives that ARs can potentially achieve are recognized. In recent years, there has been considerable progress in the application of multicriteria analysis to fisheries management (Mardle and Pascoe, 1999; Mardle et al, 2004), and within this multi-criteria analysis it may be useful for the AR socio-economic effects to the bio-economic effects (Whitmarsh et al., 2008) as a result of including the additional requirement of its environmentally sustainable production. In any case, the coefficients that weigh each of the possible effects will be obtained through experimentation

Fig. 7- Consideration of functional and economic implementation factors. Source: Prepared by the authors

4.2 Economic factors - construction and exploitation costs

For each location X_j there will be corresponding installation (CAPEX) and operation (OPEX) costs that will depend on the distance to the chosen site from the base port (d_j), as well as the existing depth (h_j) that will condition the installation. So, based on the gross benefits derived from that location, if we discount the CAPEX and OPEX costs, we will obtain the net benefits derived from the chosen location (Fig. 7).

4.2.1 CAPEX

The capital costs will derive from the consideration of several components; **conception and definition, design and development, prefabrication and installation** (table 6).

$$CAPEX = \text{Conception and Definition} + \text{Design and Development} + \text{Manufacturing Costs} + \text{Installing Costs} \quad (3)$$

$$CAPEX = C1 + C2 + C3 + C4 \quad (4)$$

Table 6. It contains the components related to the CAPEX for the installation of the AR group.

Source: own

Costs Components - CAPEX			
C1	C2	C3	C4
CONCEPTION AND DEFINITION	DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT	MANUFACTURING	INSTALLING
-Design AR Group -C11 economic feasibility study (C_{efs}) -C12 law factors (C_{taxes}) -C13 entry design of AR group (C_{hs} , C_{bs} , C_{chs})	-Engineering project -C2 detailed engineering (C_{de})	-C31- AR. Production ($C_{AR_{production}}$) -C32- AR. Protection ($C_{AR_{protection}}$)	-C41 Terrestrial Transport (C_{et}) -C42 Operation at the Base Port (C_{oh}) -C43 Maritime Transport (C_{mt}) -C44 Descent (C_{ach}) -C45 Signalling (C_s)
VARIABLES			
-Area AR group -Number of Modules (NAR_{pr} , NAR_{pt})		-Materials Cost (C_{mc}) -Direct labour Cost (C_{dle}) -Activity Cost (C_a)	-Manufacturing area -Port distance dbase-port - dj port –anchoring - Hj - depth

Conception and definition

Corresponding to the costs incurred in the initial phases of the project, we must consider; the study of *economic viability* (C11), *legal factors* (C12) and *the design of each AR group* (C13). The latter should include the hydrodynamic characterization of the study area as well as biological and geomorphological studies

$$C1 = C11 + C12 + C13 \quad (5)$$

where each of the components will be broken down according to the expressions (6), (7) and (8) that consider the costs of the economic feasibility study (C_{efs}), the occupation rates (C_{taxes}), $C_{hydrodynamic}$ study (C_{hs}), $C_{biological}$ study (C_{bs}) and $C_{characterization}$ of seabed (C_{chs})

$$C11 = C_{efs} \quad (6)$$

$$C12 = C_{taxes} * Area Polygon \quad (7)$$

$$C13 = C_{hs} + C_{bs} + C_{chs} \quad (8)$$

Design and Development

This must include the detailed engineering required for the definition of the AR groups including production and protection modules and the complete logistic study ($C_{detailed}$ engineering)

$$C2 = C_{detailed\ engineering} \quad (9)$$

Manufacturing cost

This will correspond to the manufacturing costs of the production modules (C31) and protection (C32)

$$C3 = C31 + C32 \quad (10)$$

$$C31 = CAR_{production} * NAR_{production} \quad (11)$$

$$C32 = CAR_{protection} * NAR_{protection} \quad (12)$$

Where NAR_{pr} is the number of production AR and NAR_{pt} the number of AR intended for protection.

There are two different approaches in the supply chain, one based on the existence of a central place specialized in the construction of modules and the corresponding transport to each coastal space in which rehabilitation is considered, and a second option with the production in the local port area next to the area that is to be rehabilitated.

In relation to the corresponding costs (C31, C32) these will depend on the chosen strategy, with one set of values for the construction in a centralized inland location (C311, C312) and a different set of values in the case of construction at the port that is the base of operations (C321, C322). $C_{materials}$ refers to the concrete and concrete reinforcement, while in the case of a protection AA $C'_{materials}$ it also includes the cost of the corresponding steel. The cost of materials (C_m), the cost of direct labour (C_{dl}) and the indirect costs (C_{ac}) and industrial profit (b)

$$C311 = (C_m + C_{dl} + C_{ac})(1 + b) \quad (13)$$

$$C312 = (C'_m + C_{dl} + C_{ac})(1 + b) \quad (14)$$

1 Depending on the strategies considered, we must take into account differentiated direct
2 costs and activity costs, as well as the incorporation of the costs of occupation of the
3 port surface that the port manager charges (C_{port})

$$C_{321} =$$

10 ***Installation cost***

11 This corresponds with the fourth stage in the process of construction of the AR group.

12
13
14
15
16 The components are terrestrial transport (C_{41}), the costs of handling at the origin and at
17 the base port (C_{42}), maritime transport (C_{43}), the cost of submerging the modules
18 (C_{44}) together with the cost of signalling the AR groups at the surface (C_{45}).

19
20
21
22
23
24 (19)

25
26
27
28
29 (21)

30
31
32
33
34 These expressions have the following coefficients, C_t - unit cost of terrestrial transport,
35 C_c - cost of the crane on land and C_{fc} - floating crane, C_{tm} - unit cost of maritime
36 transport, where $d_{base-port}$ and $d_{port-anchoring}$ are the distances between the place of
37 manufacture of the modules, the base port and the final anchoring location. In each case
38 the duration of the use of the floating crane for anchoring the modules will depend on
39 the depth of each area (h_j). $C_{signalling}$ the signalling and beaconing of each affected AR
40 group of the number of existing AR groups in the study area.

41 4.2.2 OPEX

42
43
44
45
46
47 Operating costs will derive from the consideration of several components; scientific
48 supervision and exploitation.

49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58 Table 7. It contains the components related to the OPEX for the installation of the AR group. Source:
59
60 Own

Costs components - OPEX	
C5	C6
SCIENTIFIC SUPERVISION	EXPLOITING
-C51 Divers costs (C_{diving}) -C52 Biology Laboratory Costs ($C_{biology\ laboratory}$)	-C61 Preventive maintenance -C62 Corrective maintenance
Variables	
-Number of samples -Number of divers	-AR group distance (dj) -

Scientific Supervision costs

This will correspond to the costs derived from the monitoring of the evolution of the AR carried out by biologists, and is related to the costs derived from the immersions for the collection of samples (C51) and the corresponding characterization works in the laboratory (C52) (table 7)

$$C5 = C51 + C52 \quad (25)$$

$$C51 = C_{diving} \cdot N_{inspection} \cdot N_{number\ of\ divers} \quad (26)$$

$$C52 = C_{biology\ laboratory} \cdot N_{number\ of\ samples} \quad (27)$$

Where $N_{inspections}$ – is the number of inspections to be carried out. $N_{number\ of\ divers}$ – the number of inspections per year to be carried out and $C_{AR\ diving}$ the cost of each dive.

$C_{biology\ laboratory}$ – cost per sample from the biology laboratory and $N_{number\ of\ samples}$ – the number of samples collected in a year

Exploiting costs

Whether the maintenance is preventive or replacive, the expression of this cost item will be composed of the costs of the materials to be replaced (CM_m), its transport cost affected by the distance to be travelled between the base port and the location of the AR group ($C_{Mtm} \cdot D_{port-anchoring}$) and direct and indirect labour (C_{dl} , C_{ac}) (Castro-Santos et al, 2016); (Castro-Santos et al, 2017)

$$C6 = C61 + C62 = (C_{Mtm} \cdot d_{port-anchoring} + CM_m + C_{dl} + C_{ac}) \quad (28)$$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Procedure description

The selection of the appropriate locations for the installation of the AR is done through the DBMS that contains all the information that was collected and generated (Section 3). In the same way, the management system incorporates a series of computational algorithms that allow easy manipulation and the determination of parameters of interest facilitating the decision-making process (Sections 3 and 4). To this end, the selection of

1 the locations is made in three differentiated phases (Phases I, II and III), through which
2 the possible valid areas for the installation of an AR group are filtered. Below, we
3 describe the phases carried out and the results obtained.

4 5 **5.2. Phase I: Excluding and morphological factors**

6
7 In this initial phase, the locations are selected based on two requirements. First, they are
8 not affected by excluding factors, that is, the installation of an AR in these areas is not
9 incompatible with the development of existing coastal uses. Secondly, they fulfil the
10 functional conditions related to the morphological characteristics, that is, the depth and
11 type of sea bottom are appropriate. As a result of the integration of these two factors, a
12 total of six areas (1-6) located approximately in the middle part of the estuary meeting
13 these requirements are identified. The locations of these areas, together with the
14 distribution of the considered uses, as well as the morphological characteristics analysed
15 are shown in **Figures 8 and 9**, respectively.

32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42 Fig. 8 - Areas selected after first step and coastal uses in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos (DBMS view).

Fig. 9 - Areas selected after first step and morphological characteristics of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos (DBMS view).

Within the selected areas, it should be mentioned that, while areas 1 and 2 are close to the limit established as adequate depth for the operation of an AR with these characteristics, they are considered based on the explicit indication provided by the Regional Authority (Xunta de Galicia) due to their special interest resulting from their proximity to the Port of Lorbé.

On the other hand, in spite of the fact that the selected areas do not currently present any limitation in relation to a potential interference with the existing uses, or derived from their morphological characteristics, a possible intensification of an existing activity in the future, or morphological variations in the medium or long term due to sediment transport processes, could result in an interference amongst uses (Álvarez et al., 2017). In order to be able to evaluate such interferences or restrictions, Table 8 shows the distance of the selected areas to the current uses located within less than 1 km, as well as the density of the existing maritime traffic. Similarly, Table 9 shows the most relevant morphological characteristics, and more specifically, the depth range and composition of the sediment of the bottom in the previously selected areas.

Table 8. Distance from the areas selected to coastal uses located at less than 1 km

Zone	Uses of the coastal zones		
	Distance	Uses	Marine Traffic Density
1	76 m	Mussel farms	High
	428 m	Natura 2000 (CIS)	
	700 m	Aquaculture area	
2	25 m	Wrecks	Very high
	560 m	Mussel farms	
3	130 m	Mussel farms	High
	350 m	Aquaculture area	
4	76 m	Wrecks	Low
	286 m	Bivalve conservation area	
5	286 m	Bivalve conservation area	Medium/High

Table 9. Morphological characteristics of the areas selected

Zone	Depth (m)	% Grain size class
1	18-23	100 % Coarse sand
2	19-22	100 % Medium sand
3	10-14	100 % Fine sand
4	10-12	31 % Fine sand 69 % Very fine sand
5	10.5-16	50 % Fine sand 50 % Very fine sand
6	10-19	21 % Medium sand 89 % Fine sand

From the information presented in [Tables 8 y 9](#), it can be seen that zones 1, 2, 3 and 5 present a potential interference with maritime traffic. In order to analyse this possible interference in more detail, the fishermen's association of the Ports of Ares and Lorbé was consulted, since they are the main users. Based on the information provided, zone 5 is considered as not appropriate for the installation of an AR. Zones 1-4 and 6 are therefore retained for further analysis.

Finally, it is important to take into consideration that the information presented in [Tables 8 y 9](#) as well as any other information contained within the DBMS can be used by the Regional Authority for the final decision-making.

5.3. Phase II: Hydrodynamic factors

The numerical results obtained in the three case studies (A, B and C) ([Section 3](#)) are incorporated into the DBMS and used to analyse the areas that were selected in Phase I. [Figures 10 and 11](#) show the distribution of the velocity field in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos in Case A (average conditions in the absence of wind and waves), for the situation of greater magnitude of the velocity of the currents during spring tides and neap tides, respectively, which corresponds to the situations defined ([Section 3](#)) for obtaining the parameters V_s and V_n .

Fig. 10 - Magnitude and direction of peak velocities in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos during spring tides (approximately at mid-ebb) under mean conditions (Case A) (DBMS view).

Fig. 11 - Magnitude and direction of peak velocities in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos during neap tides (approximately at mid-ebb) under mean conditions (Case A) (DBMS view).

The situation of greater magnitude of the currents in average conditions is obtained approximately at mid ebb tide. In general terms, it can be established that the magnitude of the velocity increases gradually towards the upper part of the estuary, where velocities of up to 1 ms^{-1} occur in the narrowest and shallowest sections, which in any case are very localized and do not correspond to the areas of interest for the installation of an AR (Section 5.2). In addition, the velocity of the currents tends to present higher values in the vicinity of closed contours (coastal limits), which is probably the result of the lower depth, in contrast to the more central channel of greater depth. This situation becomes more evident during neap tides (Figure 11). As for the middle Ria, where the

1 previously selected zones are located, it presents maximum current magnitudes between
2 0.2 ms^{-1} in spring tides and 0.1 ms^{-1} in neap tides, results that are coherent with those
3 previously obtained in this Ria as presented in [Section 3 \(Piedracoba et al., 2005\)](#).

4 In relation to the action of the wind (Case B) and waves (Case C), the circulation
5 induced by these forcings acting solely is presented in [Figures 12 y 13](#), respectively.

31 Fig. 12- Wind-induced circulation in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos (Case B) (DBMS view).

53 Fig. 13- Wave-induced circulation in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos (Case C) (DBMS view).

55 The results show that the wind is not capable of inducing a significant current velocity
56 compared to the average scenario in absence of wind (Case A), even in the case of
57 considering strong winds. In this sense, the resulting velocities are of approx. 0.01 ms^{-1} ,
58 one order of magnitude lower than the currents in an average situation in the absence of
59

wind and waves (Figure 12). However, it is expected that its capacity to generate residual currents is greater than that of the tide and freshwater discharges, representing in any case the forcing agent with greater capacity to generate upwelling processes. Finally, as it might be expected, the currents induced by the waves (Case C) (Figure 13) are relevant in the outer zone of the Ria, while in the middle Ria they are of certain interest only at very specific locations being exposed to the action of the waves.

In this way, the circulation induced by the wind and waves during non-extreme events is of much less importance than the transient circulation generated by the tide, which corroborates the results obtained in recent investigations (Piedracoba et al., 2014). For this reason, the magnitude of the currents in an average situation (Case A) is used in the present work to select the locations of interest to install an AR group.

In order to analyse more accurately the magnitude of the current velocity in the areas selected in Case A, the DBMS is used to compute the average value within each area of V_s and V_n , as established in Section 3 (Table 10).

Table 10. Mean peak current velocities during spring tides, V_s , and neap tides, V_n

Zone	V_s (ms ⁻¹)	V_n (ms ⁻¹)
1	0,194	0,058
2	0,157	0,024
3	0,204	0,058
4	0,079	0,020
6	0,146	0,042

It can be seen that areas 1 and 3 present the highest flow velocity, followed by areas 2 and 6 with a slightly lower value during spring tides and a significantly lower one during neap tides; finally, area 4 has a significantly lower magnitude of velocity in both situations. In this sense, it can be observed that there is a considerable variation between the velocities reached during spring and neap tides, a situation that results from the significant differences in the tidal range, which in turn shows that the tide is the main forcing of the hydrodynamics of the Ria de Ares-Betanzos in an average situation. In accordance with the criteria established in Section 3 regarding the magnitude of the current velocity suitable for the installation of ARs, area 4 is determined as not to be appropriate for this purpose. Therefore, zones 1, 2, 3 and 6 are retained for analysis in Phase 3.

It is necessary to bear in mind that the described hydrodynamic patterns causes the transport of sediments which is responsible for the changes in the morphology of the estuary. Similarly, a detailed analysis of the wind-induced circulation and its importance in generating upwelling processes, as well as its influence on the operational capacity of ARs, requires the implementation of 3D models. This information could be used in the decision-making process, so its future inclusion in the DBMS is considered.

5.4. Phase III: Economic factors

In addition to the aforementioned factors, economic factors play a fundamental role in the selection of the most appropriate areas for installing an AR. These depend on, among other aspects, the depth of the operation (H_j), as well as the distance to the nearest port (d_j), in this case Ares and Lorbé, and the total available surface available for its installation (*AR Group Area*). In the present phase 3 the costs are calculated according to the procedure presented in Section 3, through which the parameters related to the conditions contained in the DBMS are obtained (Table 11).

Table 11. Main characteristics of the areas selected for an economic analysis

Zone	Depth (m)	Area (ha)	Distance to Lorbé Port (km)	Distance to Ares Port (km)
1	18-23	39.67	1.61	4.81
2	19-22	19.49	2.01	4.02
3	10-14	43.39	2.70	4.13
6	10-19	15.71	4.86	4.28

In order to establish an economic criterion that allows us to determine the most suitable locations, we must consider the components that are dependent on the locations under study. Specifically, the CAPEX components [C11 (Area AR group), C2 (dj), C3 (dj), C43 (dj) and C44 (Hj)] and OPEX components (C51 (dj, Hj), C6 (dj)) are dependent of the AR group position variables for each zone contained in table 11 (*AR Group area, dj port -anchoring, - Hj - depth*).

For the areas under study, and considering the cost components dependent on the location together with the weighting factors that modulate the importance of each of these components, decision table 12 has been compiled. Its application shows that the options of greater interest are areas 1, 2-3 and 6 from the port of Lorbé and areas 2-3, 6 and 1 from the port of Ares (classified according to their ascending installation costs) (table 13). As a result of this third phase, zones 6 and 1 are excluded, depending on whether the base ports were Lorbé or Ares.

Table 12 - Allows the identification of areas with favourable CAPEX and OPEX costs. For each study area and based on the consideration of two base ports (Lorbé and Ares), after weighting each cost component, the areas have been classified in order, proportional to their cost (value proportional to the cost incurred, 1-low, 4-high). Source: Own

Zone	COST COMPONENTS						COST
	Capex			Opex			
	C11 (Area)	C43 (dj) Lorbé/Ares	C44 (Hj)	C51 (dj) Lorbé/Ares	C51 (Hj)	C6 (dj) Lorbé/Ares	
1	3	1/4	3.5	1/4	3.5	1/4	13
2	2	2/1	3.5	2/1	3.5	2/1	15
3	4	3/2	1	3/2	1	3/2	19
6	1	4/3	2	4/3	2	4/3	16
Weighting factor	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	

TOTAL							COST Lorbé/ Ares
1	0.3	0.3/1.2	0.7	0.2/0.8	0.35	0.1/0.4	1.65 /3.75
2	0.2	0.6/0.3	0.7	0.4/0.2	0.35	0.2/0.1	2.45 /1.85
3	0.4	0.9/0.6	0.2	0.6/0.4	0.1	0.3/0.2	2.5/1.9
6	0.1	1.2/0.9	0.4	0.8/0.6	0.2	0.4/0.3	3.1/2.5

Table 13. Finalist areas in accordance with base ports as a result of applying the DBMS tool.

PORT AREA	Best option zone	Second option zone	Deleted zone
Lorbé	1	2-3	6
Ares	2-3	6	1

6. CONCLUSIONS

The methodology described in the present research allows an informed decision-making for positioning AR groups based on the consideration of production factors grouped by types of conditions: excluding, functional (bathymetric, geomorphological, technical) and economic factors related to construction and maintenance.

With this in view, the selection of the appropriate locations for the installation of the AR is done through the so-called DBMS (database management system) that contains all the information that was collected and generated. In the same way, this management system incorporates a series of computational algorithms that allow easy manipulation and the determination of parameters of interest that facilitate the decision-making. In this way, the selection of the locations is made in three differentiated phases (Phase I: excluding and morphological factors, Phase II: hydrodynamic factors and Phase III: economic factors), through which the possible valid areas for the installation of an AR group are progressively filtered.

In the application to the Ria de Ares-Betanzos, from Phase I a total of six areas (1-6) emerge as possible sites for installing an AR group, being location 5 disregarded after consulting the fishermen's association of the Ports of Ares and Lorbé. By analysing through numerical modelling the hydrodynamics of this Ría, and in particular the selected areas (Phase II), it can be seen that areas 1 and 3 have the highest flow velocity, followed by areas 2 and 6 with a slightly lower value during spring tides and significantly lower during neap tides; finally, area 4 has a significantly lower magnitude of velocity in both situations. In this sense, it can be observed that there is a considerable variation between the velocities attained during spring and neap tides, a situation that results from the significant differences in the tidal range which in turn

1 shows that the tide is the main forcing agent of the hydrodynamics of the Ria de Ares-
2 Betanzos in an average situation. In accordance with the criteria established in Section 3
3 regarding the magnitude of the current velocity suitable for the installation of ARs, area
4 4 emerges as not appropriate for this purpose. Therefore, zones 1, 2, 3 and 6 are retained
5 for analysis in Phase 3.
6

7 Finally, the economic factors play a fundamental role in the selection of the most
8 suitable area to install an AR, since after determining which areas are suitable and
9 generate similar potential benefits (those that pass phases 1 and 2), the most favourable
10 ones will be those that present lower costs. The installation and maintenance costs
11 depend, among other aspects, on the total area available for installation, the depth of
12 operation and the distance to the nearest ports, in this case Ares and Lorbé. Considering
13 the areas under study, the cost components depending on the location and the weighting
14 factors that modulate the importance of each component, the areas that are selected as
15 the most interesting options are areas 1, 2 and 3, using Lorbé as the base port and the
16 areas 2, 3 and 6 in case of using Ares.
17
18
19
20
21

22 **Acknowledgements**

23 The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the regional government
24 of Galicia, Xunta de Galicia, through the project CN-10MMA003CT.
25

26 The authors are grateful to Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) and Instituto
27 Técnico para o Control do Medio Mariño de Galicia (Intecmar) for providing the
28 ocean uses and environmental information; to Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina
29 (IHM) and Sociedade para o Desenvolvemento Comarcal de Galicia (SITGA) for the
30 bathymetric and topographic data, respectively; and to Puertos del Estado for the wave
31 buoy data records.
32
33
34
35
36
37

38 **BIBLIOGRAPHY**

39
40
41 Aller, Robert C., and Richard E Dodge. 1974. "Animal-Sediment Relations in a
42 Tropical Lagoon: Discovery Bay, Jamaica." *Journal of Marine Research* 32(2): 209–32.
43

44
45 Álvarez, M., Carballo, R., Ramos, V., Iglesias, G., 2017. An integrated approach for the
46 planning of dredging operations in estuaries. *Ocean Engineering* 140, 73-83.
47

48
49 Alvarez-Salgado, X.A., Figueiras, F.G., Fernandez-Reiriz, M.J., Labarta, U., Peteiro, L.,
50 Piedracoba, S., 2011. Control of lipophilic shellfish poisoning outbreaks by seasonal
51 upwelling and continental runoff. *Harmful Algae* 10, 121e129.
52

53
54 Asensio-Amor, I. & Grajal-Blanco, M., 1981. Rasgos morfológicos y sedimentológicos
55 de la Ria de Betanzos (A Coruña, Galicia, España). *Cuadernos do Laboratorio*
56 *Xeolóxico de Laxe*, 2, 197 - 208.
57

58
59 Bacher, C., Grant, J., Hawkins, A.J.S., Fang, J., Zhu, M. & Besnard, M. 2003.
60 Modelling the effect of food depletion on scallop growth in Sungo Bay (China).
61
62
63
64
65

Aquatic Living Resources, 16(1): 10–24.

Blanco, J., 1985. Algunas características del fitoplancton de Lorbe (Ría de Ares y Betanzos) en primavera. *Bol. Inst. Español Oceanogr.* 2, 17 - 26.

Barnabe, G. Barnabe-Quet R. - 2000 - Science The Aquatic Environment Gilbert *Barnabe*, Regine *Barnabe-Quet*. Professor ... Praxis Publishing Ltd, Chichester, UK, 2000

Bode, A., Varela, M., 1998. Primary production and phytoplankton in three Galician Rías Altas (NW Spain): seasonal and spatial variability. *Sci. Mar.* 62, 319 - 330.

Booij, N., Ris, R.C., Holthuijsen, L.H., 1999. A third-generation wave model for coastal regions 1. Model description and validation. *Journal of Geophysical Research C: Oceans* 104, 7649-7666.

Bowden, K.F., 1980. Physical factors: salinity, temperature, circulation and mixing processes. In *Chemistry and biochemistry of estuaries* (ed. E. Olauson and I. Cato), pp. 223 - 245. Chichester: JohnWiley & Sons.

Carballo, R., Iglesias, G., Castro, A., 2009a. Numerical model evaluation of tidal stream energy resources in the Ría de Muros (NW Spain). *Renewable Energy* 34, 1517-1524.

Carballo, R., Iglesias, G., Castro, A., 2009b. Residual circulation in the Ría de Muros (NW Spain): A 3D numerical model study. *J. Mar. Syst.* 75, 130-130.

Carballo, R., Sánchez, M., Ramos, V., Taveira-Pinto, F., Iglesias, G., 2014. A high resolution geospatial database for a wave energy exploitation. *Energy* 68, 572-583.

Carral L., Rodríguez-Guerreiro M, Tarrio-Saavedra J., Álvarez-Feal J. C., Fraguela Formoso J. 2018a. Social interest in developing a Green modular artificial reef structure in concrete for the ecosystems of the Galician rías. *Journal of Cleaner Production.* 172-1881-1898.

Carral Couce L, Rodríguez Guerreiro M.J, Fraguela Formoso J.A., Álvarez-Feal J.C., Filgueira Vizoso A. 2018b. “Green artificial reef proarr: repopulation of coastal ecosystems and waste recycler of the maritime industries”, *Proceedings of the 25th Pan-American Conference of Naval Engineering – COPINAVAL*. Springer International Publishing

Carter, R.W.G., 1988. Coastal environments. An introduction to the physical, ecological and cultural systems of coastlines. London: Academic Press.

Castro-Santos L., Luis Carral Couce, Filgueira Vizoso A., José Ángel Fraguela Formoso. 2016. Economic feasibility of floating offshore wind farms. *ENERGY* Vol. 2016 (págs. 868 a 882)

1 Castro Santos L, Filgueira A, Carral Couce L., Lamas-Galdo I. 2017. Methodology to
2 calculate the installation costs of offshore wind farms located in deep waters. Journal of
3 cleaner production Vol. 170 (págs. 1124 a 1135)

4
5 Duarte, P., Fernandez-Reiriz, M.J., Labarta, U., 2012. Modelling mussel growth
6 inecosystems with low suspended matter loads using a Dynamic Energy
7 Budgetapproach. J. Sea Res. 67, 44-57.
8

9
10 Ferreño S., Carral L., Guerreiro M. Fraguela J, Villa R. 2012 Estudio, análisis y
11 valorización de residuos industriales procedentes de la industria de la construcción
12 naval, para su reciclaje y uso en otras aplicaciones marinas. VII Simposio Marítimo -
13 Symtechnaval – La Habana -Cuba
14

15
16 Grant, J., Bacher, C., 2001. A numerical model of flow modification induced by
17 suspended aquaculture in a Chinese Bay. Can. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci. 58, 1-9.
18

19
20 Grant, J., Stenton-Dozey, J., Monteiro, P., Pitcher, G., Heasman, K., 1998. Shellfish
21 culture in the Benguela system: a carbon budget of Saldanha Bay for raft culture of
22 *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. J. Shellfish Res. 17, 41-49.
23

24
25 Haroun, Ricardo, and Rogelio Herrera. 2000. “Artificial Reefs of the Canary Islands.”
26 In *Artificial Reefs in European Seas*, Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 235–47.
27 http://www.springerlink.com/index/10.1007/978-94-011-4215-1_14 (July 16, 2018).
28

29
30 Iglesias, G., Carballo, R., 2011. Can the seasonality of a small river affect a large tide-
31 dominated estuary? The case of the Ria de Viveiro, Spain. J. Coast. Res. 27, 1170-1182.
32

33
34 Iglesias, G., Carballo, R., 2010. Effects of high winds on the circulation of the using a mixed
35 open boundary condition: the Ria de Muros, Spain. Environmental Modelling & Software 25,
36 455-466.
37

38
39 Iglesias, G., Carballo, R., 2009. Seasonality of the circulation in the Ria de Muros (NW Spain).
40 J. Mar. Syst. 78, 94-108.
41

42
43 Iglesias, G., Carballo, R., Castro, A., 2008. Baroclinic modelling and analysis of tide- and wind-
44 induced circulation in the Ria de Muros (NW Spain). J. Mar. Syst. 74, 475-484.
45

46
47 Iglesias, G., Sánchez, M., Carballo, R., Fernández, H., 2012. The TSE index – A new tool for
48 selecting tidal stream sites in depth-limited regions. Renewable Energy 48, 350-357.
49

50
51 Labarta, U., Fernandez-Reiriz, M.J., Perez-Camacho, A., Perez-Corbacho, E.,
52 2004. Bateiros, Mar, Mejillon. Una Perspectiva Bioeconomica (Serie Estudios
53 Sectoriales). Fundacion CaixaGalicia, A Coruna, España.
54

55
56 Lamas Galdo MI., Townsed P., Rodriguez Guerreiro MJ., Castro Santos L., Carral
57 Couce L. Numerical model to analyze an artificial reef. Submitted to XXVI Pan-
58 American Conference on Naval Engineering, COPINAVAL 2019.
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 Loya, Y. 1972. "Community Structure and Species Diversity of Hermatypic Corals at
2 Eilat, Red Sea." *Marine Biology* 13(2): 100-123.

3 Mardle S, Pascoe S. 1999. A review of applications of multicriteria decision making
4 techniques to fisheries. *Marine Resource Economics* 1999;14:41–63.

5 Mardle S, Pascoe S, Herrero I. 2004. Management objective importance in fisheries: an
6 evaluation using the analytic hierarchy process. *Environmental Management*
7 2004;33(1):1–11.

8 Mariño, J., Campos, M., Nunes, M., Iglesias, M., 1985. Variacion estacional de los
9 actores ambientales y del fitoplancton en la zona de Lorbe (Ría de Ares y Betanzos) en
10 1978. *Bol. Inst. Españ. Oceanogr.* 2, 88 - 99.

11 McLusky, D.S., 1989. *The estuarine ecosystem*. New York: Chapman & Hall.

12 Milton JW, Holland SM, Whitmarsh DJ. 2000. Social and economic valuation methods.
13 In: Seaman W, editor. *Artificial reef evaluation with application to natural marine*
14 *habitats*. CRC Press; 2000. p. 165–94.

15 Mora, J. et al., 1994. Perturbaciones ocasionadas por los hidrocarburos vertidos en el
16 naufragio del Aegean Sea. Estudio de la fauna bentonica. 1. Estudio de la macrofauna
17 submareal de la Ría de Ares-Betanzos. Technical Report. Ministerio de Obras Publicas
18 yTransportes, Madrid.

19 Mora, J., 1980. Poblaciones bentonicas de la Ría de Arosa. PhD thesis, Universidad de
20 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

21 Pears R.J. and Williams, D.M., Potential effects of artificial reefs on the Great Barrier
22 Reef: Background paper, 60, pp. 1-33, 2005.

23 Perkol-Finkel, S. et al. 2007. "Floating and Fixed Artificial Habitats: Spatial and
24 Temporal Patterns of Benthic Communities in a Coral Reef Environment." *Estuarine,*
25 *Coastal and Shelf Science* 77(3): 491–500.

26 Peteiro, L.G., Labarta, U., Fernandez-Reiriz, M.J., Alvarez-Salgado, X.A., Filgueira,
27 R., Piedracoba, S., 2011. Influence of intermittent-upwelling on *Mytilus*
28 *galloprovincialis* settlement patterns in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.*
29 443, 111-127.

30 Pethick, J., 1984. *An introduction to coastal geomorphology*. London: Edward Arnold.

31 Pickering, H.; Withmarsh, D.; Jensen, A.: *Artificial reefs as a tool to aid rehabilitation*
32 *of coastal ecosystems: investigating the potential*. Reef Design and Materials
33 Workshop, Southampton, 1998.

34 Piedracoba, S., Alvarez Salgado, X.A., Labarta, U., Fernandez-Reiriz, M.J., Gomez, B.,
35 Balseiro, C., 2014. Water flows through mussel rafts and their relationship with wind

1 speed in a coastal embayment (Ria de Ares-Betanzos, NW Spain). *Continen. Shelf Res.*
2 75, 1-14.

3 Piedracoba, S., Alvarez-Salgado, X.A., Roson, G., Herrera, J.L., 2005. Short-time scale
4 thermohaline variability and residual circulation in the central segment of the coastal
5 upwelling system of the ría de Vigo (northwest Spain) during four contrasting periods.
6 *J. Geophys. Res.* 110 (C03018), 1-15.

7
8
9
10 Prego, R. & Fraga, F., 1992. A simple model to calculate the residual flows in a Spanish
11 ria. *Hydrographic consequences in the Ria of Vigo. Estuarine and Coastal and Shelf*
12 *Science*, 34, 603 - 615.

13
14
15 Prego R., Barciela MC, Varela M, 1999. Nutrient dynamics in the Galician coastal area
16 (Northwestern Iberian Peninsula): Do the Rias Bajas receive more nutrient salts than the
17 Rias Altas, *Continental Shelf Research*, Volume 19, Issue 3, Pages 317-334,

18
19
20 Rodríguez-Guerreiro, MJ* Álvarez-Feal, JC, Fraguera-Formoso, JA, Castro-Santos L.
21 Carral-Couce L 2019. Application of a general pattern of colonization of a “verde-
22 PROARR” artificial reef in the Ria de Ares-Betanzos (Spain). Submitted in Proceedings
23 of the 26th Pan-American Conference of Naval Engineering – COPINAVAL. Springer
24 International Publishing

25
26
27
28 Sanchez-Mata, A., Glemarec, M., Mora, J., 1999. Physico-chemical structure of the
29 benthic environment of a Galician Ria (Ria de Ares-Betanzos, north-west Spain). *J.*
30 *Mar. Biol. Assoc. U.K.* 79, 1-21.

31
32
33 Seaman, W. Jr.; Buckley, R.M.; Polovina, J.J.: Advances in knowledge and priorities
34 for research, technology and management related to artificial aquatic habitats. *Bulletin*
35 *of Marine Science*, vol. 44 (2), pp. 527-532, 1989.

36
37
38 Seaman W. Unifying trends and opportunities in global artificial reef research,
39 including evaluation. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 2002; 59:S14–6.

40
41
42 Seaman, W., Artificial habitats and the restoration of degraded marine ecosystems and
43 fisheries, *Hydrobiologia*, 580(1), pp. 143-155, 2007. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-006-0457-9

44
45
46 Shi, J., Wei, H., Zhao, L., Yuan, Y., Fang, J., Zhang, J., 2011. A physico-biological
47 coupled aquaculture model for a suspended aquaculture area of China. *Aquaculture* 318,
48 412 - 424.

49
50
51 Smith S. V., K. J. Roy, H. G. Schesser, G. L. Shepherd and K. E. Chave. 1971. “Flux of
52 Suspended Calcium Carbonate (CaCO₃),” *Pacific Science*: 206–21.

53
54
55 Troncoso, J.S & Ugorri, V. (1993). Datos sedimentológicos y macrofauna de los fondos
56 infralitorales de sustrato blando de la Ría de Ares y Betanzos (Galicia,España). *Nova Acta*
57 *Científica Compostelana (Biología)*, 4: 153-166.

58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 Turner RK, Adger WN. 1996. Coastal zone resources assessment guidelines. Land–
2 ocean interactions in the coastal zone. Reports and studies No. 4. IGBP/LOICZ. Texel:
3 the Netherlands; 1996. p. ivp101
4

5 User Manual Delft3D-FLOW, 2010. Deltares ed., Delft, The Netherlands.
6

7 Villegas-Ríos, D, Álvarez-Salgado XA, Piedracoba S, Rosón, G, Labarta, U. , 2011 Net
8 ecosystem metabolism of a coastal embayment fertilised by upwelling and continental
9 runoff. Continental Shelf Research 31 (5), 400-413
10

11 Whitmarsh, D., Santos, M.N., Ramos, J., Monteiro, C.C., 2008. Marine
12 habitatmodification through artificial reefs off the Algarve (southern Portugal):
13 aneconomic analysis of the fisheries and the prospects for management. OceanCoast.
14 Manage. 51 (6), 463–468.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65